

Work Package 1

Identification of Material Property Data for Later Analysis

Deliverable D1.2

Material Properties and Data of the Pilot Project

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Foreword

QuaDeSIM is a pilot project under the umbrella of the Joint Program on Nuclear Materials (JPNM) of the European Energy Research Alliance (EERA). QuaDeSIM aims to contribute to creating an effective process to generate structured, qualified material data that can be used to underpin structural integrity calculations.

Work Package 1 aims to create a future for historic materials data by 1/ (completing) entry of selected data into a repository, MatDB; 2/ addressing the needed features of the repository; and 3/ establishing the long-term prospects of the repository and its materials data.

This deliverable is the outcome of Task 1 of Work Package 1, namely it gives an overview of the MatDB repository holdings that are accessible to the pilot project, for the selected test types, uniaxial tensile and general corrosion. The contributions stem from various partners, as graphically displayed.

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Introduction

With the objective of collecting a sufficiently large body of data for the work anticipated in Work Packages 2 and 3, the data gathering exercise began with a survey of test results that could potentially be made available. Thereafter, attention was given to uploading the test results to MatDB. Where test results were already available from MatDB, they were examined for correctness and on occasion curated as necessary.

In parallel with the data gathering tasks, the Data Committee (featuring in Work Package 3) developed data protocols and accompanying data schemas in anticipation of rating both the completeness and the quality of the test results. As well as facilitating ratings, the work by the Data Committee also identified opportunities to update and improve MatDB.

Method

Data Gathering Survey

The data gathering survey was formulated on the basis of the materials, test types and conditions of immediate interest, namely of relevance to the qualification of materials likely to find application in liquid-metal cooled reactors, as follows:

- Materials – P91, 304L, 316L and 15-15 Ti.
- Test types – uniaxial tensile, SSRT/CERT and corrosion.
- Conditions (uniaxial tensile) – surface finish, environment, strain rate and temperature.
- Conditions (SSRT/CERT) – surface finish, environment, strain rate, temperature, oxygen content, pre-exposure time and pre-exposure temperature.
- Conditions (corrosion) – surface finish, environment, time, temperature, oxygen content, pre-exposure time and pre-exposure temperature.

Data Collection and Curation

With the data gathering survey having identified the test results that could potentially be made available, test results were then uploaded to MatDB or curated in the circumstance of having been uploaded already.

Results

Data Gathering Survey

The data gathering survey was undertaken over a period of approximately 18 months, ending September 2024. A summary of the results at the close of the survey is shown in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Partner	Tensile	SSRT	Corrosion	Total	Materials	Projects	Comments
CIEMAT	6	8		14	15-15 Ti	GEMMA (EU)	MatDB published/total: 4/6 uniaxial tensile 4/8 SSRT
CNRS	13	49		62	15-15 Ti AFA	GEMMA (EU)	MatDB published/total: 13/13 uniaxial tensile 49/49 SSRT
CVR		37	50	87	316L 15-15 Ti EUROFER T91	EUROTRANS (EU) GEMMA (EU) LEADER (EU) VELLA (EU) National Institutional	MatDB published/total: 50/50 general corrosion 37/37 SSRT
ENEA	32	25	38	95	15-15 AlM1 316L 316L(N) base material, filler material and welded joints FeCr model alloys	GEMMA (EU)	MatDB published/total: 32/32 uniaxial tensile 38/38 general corrosion 25/25 SSRT
JRC	48	12		60	316L(N) base material, filler material and welded joints	GEMMA (EU) MATTER (EU)	MatDB published/total: 18/38 uniaxial tensile 0/0 SSRT
KIT-IHM			36	36	15-15 Ti 316L 316L(N) T91	EUROTRANS (EU) GEMMA (EU) Institutional	MatDB published/total: 17/17 general corrosion
KIT-IAM			99	99	316L T91	EUROTRANS (EU) GEMMA (EU) MATTER (EU)	MatDB published/total: 12/12 general corrosion
NRG	41			41	15-15 Ti (LBE exposed) T91 Zircaloy-4	GETMAT (EU) PATRICIA (EU) TASTE+ (JPNM)	MatDB published/total: 37/41 uniaxial tensile
SCK	138	154	14	306	316L (base material, filler material and welded joints) P91	GEMMA (EU) MATTER (EU)	MatDB published/total: 134/138 14/14 general corrosion 139/154 SSRT
	278	285	237	800			

Table 1. Summary of the results of the data gathering survey.

Figure 1. Summary of the results of the data gathering survey, with colour-coding to indicate the eventual correspondence with the test results available from MatDB at the close of the data collection and curation exercise, where green, orange and red indicate good, fair and poor correspondence, respectively.

Data Collection and Curation

With the data gathering survey having identified the data that could potentially be made available, the test results were then uploaded to MatDB (or curated in the circumstance of having been uploaded already) over a period of approximately 18 months, ending September 2025.

Summaries of the results at the close of the data collection and curation exercises are shown in Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4, for each of the uniaxial tensile, SSRT/CERT and corrosion test types, respectively.

Figure 2. Summary of the uniaxial test results available from MatDB at the close of the data collection and curation exercise.

Figure 3. Summary of the SSRT/CERT test results available from MatDB at the close of the data collection and curation exercise.

Figure 4. Summary of the corrosion test results available from MatDB at the close of the data collection and curation exercise.

Data Access

To access any of the openly accessible data belonging to the collections shown in Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4, navigate to <https://odin.jrc.ec.europa.eu> and choose the ‘Open Access’ item from the ‘MatDB’ main menu. Thereafter, choose the test type and material(s) of interest. Next, click the ‘Advanced selection’ button and make a selection from the ‘Company name’ list on the names of the QuaDeSIM project partners. Finally, make a selection from the ‘Environment’ list to distinguish the air or liquid lead test results. To view and further examine the selection, click the ‘Generate report’ button.

An alternative and more convenient mechanism for reviewing and accessing the collections shown in Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4, will be possible in the circumstance corresponding DOI catalogs are created. Such catalogs will serve a number of useful purposes, as follows:

- Using the preselection feature available from the data retrieval module, a preliminary selection can be made immediately on all the test results listed in a particular catalog .
- A catalog can be referenced (using a citation similar to that for a traditional publication) in a scientific article or technical report, which is particularly important in the circumstance

that a third party is interested to perform assessments using the exact same collection of data.

- A catalog lists all irrespective of whether Open Access or restricted-access test results, so there is a clear understanding of the extent of the data even if some test results are not available (due to insufficient privileges).

Discussion

As on a prior occasion at OECD-NEA [1], the data gathering survey was undertaken with a view to establishing the extent and availability of data from mechanical tests performed in a liquid-metal environment. The overall outcome of the data gathering survey and subsequent data collection and curation exercise has been to deliver a total of approximately 800 test results. Although this represents a significant body of data, further work is required to achieve a satisfactory level of completeness and quality for the statistical analyses undertaken in Work Package 3 to yield reliable results. Further, some known shortcomings remain to be addressed, as follows:

- Specimen records have proven problematic to encode in the circumstance of multi-coupon corrosion tests and how best to encode such results requires further consideration.
- Whereas SSRT/CERT test results have been encoded using the existing uniaxial tensile data entry module, a new SSRT/CERT entry module may be required.
- The NRG tensile test results coming from the PATRICIA project correspond to the ring tensile test type and whereas the existing uniaxial tensile data entry module has been used to encode the test results, a new ring-tensile module may be required.

Where encoding the results of multi-coupon corrosion tests has proven problematic, the circumstance can be traced to the MatDB data model anticipating a one-to-one relation between a specimen record and a test result record i.e. a single specimen yields a single test result. Typically, this is an accurate reflection of the actual test configuration, especially for mechanical test types but for corrosion tests this can be problematic because taking time-series measurements from different coupons is a common testing practice. These time-series measurements are then aggregated to form a single test result. In this circumstance, multiple coupons can either be hung from a cradle or tree; occupy individual crucibles that occupy the same environment chamber; or otherwise housed together in a capsule or interconnected environmental chambers. Presently, MatDB manages this multi-coupon circumstance by treating the cradle, tree, capsule or interconnected environmental chambers as the specimen (hence preserving the aforementioned one-to-one relation). Records for individual coupons are then encoded as subsets of the corresponding specimen record. Although such an encoding is representative of the actual test configuration, potentially important characteristics of the coupons cannot be encoded, such as surface details and coatings. After some lengthy consideration, the preferred solution is to specify the multi-coupon housing (cradle, tree, multi-crucible, capsule or interconnected environmental chambers) as part of the test condition record and encode each coupon as an individual specimen record.

Together with the technical limitations, conceptually the encoding of the corrosion test results has proven challenging, with the result that (1) the data gathering survey typically includes entries for individual coupons, so there is no direct correspondence with the number of MatDB test results and (2) QuaDeSIM project partners adopted different approaches to encoding of the corrosion test results, so the encodings are inconsistent. These inconsistencies remain and will need to be addressed by the DatCom.

Where the results at the close of the data collection and curation exercises are shown in Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4, the ‘DatCom’ and ‘Rating’ metrics are absent because the data review and rating tasks of the DatCom have yet to begin.

Perhaps the most insightful outcome of the data gathering survey and subsequent data collection and curation tasks has been the extent to which existing MatDB records are incomplete or inaccurate. While this has delayed the overall project schedule by more than a year, the circumstance was entirely avoidable in the event that data curation was given proper attention at the time of testing i.e. during the project. It is reasonable to claim that not only has this circumstance adversely impacted QuaDeSIM but also makes the findings less reliable than could (and should) have been expected. Thus, the single most important conclusion coming from QuaDeSIM Work Package 1 is that all future projects on liquid-metal testing must give proper attention to data curation before project term. In this circumstance, not only would the quality and extent of data be improved but the need for projects such as QuaDeSIM to give attention to preliminary data gathering tasks would be eliminated, so that scientific activities leveraging historic data could begin immediately rather than after an extended delay.

Conclusions

The data gathering survey and subsequent data collection and curation exercise have delivered a body of data totaling approximately 800 individual test results. Although this represents a significant body of data, work must continue to improve their completeness and quality if the results of subsequent WP3 statistical analyses are to be reliable. Where the data gathering tasks have delayed the overall project schedule by more than a year, the single most important conclusion coming from QuaDeSIM Work Package 1 is that all future projects on liquid-metal testing must give proper attention to data curation before project term.

References

1. Structural Materials Data Management Survey, NEA/NSC/R(2019)3. [Online]. Available: https://www.oecd-nea.org/jcms/pl_47115/structural-materials-data-management-survey. [Accessed February 2026].